

A BRIEF REVIEW OF STUDIES ON THE AMPHIPOD (MALACOSTRACA: AMPHIPODA) FAUNA OF THE CHIRCHIK BASIN AND ADJACENT AREAS

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Annotatsiya. Maqolada Chirchiq havzasi va unga yondosh hududlardagi amfipodalar faunasi, ularning tarqalishi va morfologik xilma-xilligi haqida tarixiy manbalar asosida ma'lumot beriladi. A.V.Martynovning tadqiqotlari asosida aniqlangan turlar keltirilib, mavjud ma'lumotlarning tizimlashtirilmaganligi va yangi tadqiqotlar zarurligi ta'kidlanadi.

Kalit so'zlar: Amfipodalar, Chirchiq havzasi, biologik xilma-xillik, morfologik tavsif, Martynov tadqiqotlari.

Abstract. The article provides information, based on historical sources, about the amphipod fauna of the Chirchik Basin and adjacent areas, including their distribution and morphological diversity. Species identified through the research of A.V. Martynov are presented, and the lack of systematization in existing data as well as the need for further studies is emphasized.

Keywords: Amphipods, Chirchik Basin, biological diversity, morphological description, Martynov's research.

Аннотация. В статье на основе исторических источников представлена информация о фауне амфипод Чирчикского бассейна и прилегающих районов, их распространении и морфологическом разнообразии. Приведены виды, выявленные в результате исследований А.В.Мартынова, подчёркивается фрагментарность существующих данных и необходимость проведения новых научных исследований.

Ключевые слова: амфиподы, Чирчикский бассейн, биологическое разнообразие, морфологическое описание, исследования Мартынова.

Amphipods, representatives of higher crustaceans, are widely distributed in almost all aquatic habitats of the world – including freshwater, brackish, and marine environments – and are especially common in freshwater ecosystems such as rivers, lakes, springs, and reservoirs.

Amphipods play an important role in biological diversity. They serve as a food source for many predatory fish and other aquatic organisms. Due to their affiliation with various ecological groups, they are also used as bioindicators for assessing the condition of aquatic ecosystems. The abundance and species composition of amphipods are directly affected by water quality, pollution levels, and hydrological changes. Therefore, studying them is crucial for ensuring ecosystem stability and conducting effective environmental monitoring.

In Uzbekistan, particularly in the Chirchik Basin, data on the distribution and species diversity of amphipods remain insufficient. Existing information is fragmented, often lacks synthesis, and is not based on systematic scientific analysis.

The earliest information on amphipods was presented in a scientific work published in 1875 by Russian zoologist and professor of the University of Warsaw, V.N.Ulyanin. In this work, based on materials collected by Russian scientist and explorer A.P.Fedchenko from the Samarkand and Tashkent regions, the presence of the species *Gammarus pulex* in Central Asia, particularly in the territory of Uzbekistan, was recorded [1].

The contribution of A.V.Martynov, a prominent zoologist and researcher at the Paleontological Institute of the Russian Academy of Sciences, to the study of Central Asian amphipod fauna is

particularly noteworthy. His fundamental work «Amphipoda Gammaridea of the running waters of Turkestan» (1935) is considered a key source for the systematic description of the region's aquatic invertebrates.

As a result of A.V.Martynov's research, several new species and morphological forms belonging to the genus *Rivulogammarus* (= *Gammarus*) were identified, each of which was provided with detailed morphological and ecological descriptions [2].

- from the Chimyonsoy River in Tashkent region – *Rivulogammarus turanus* and its morphological form *morpha subnivalis*;
- from the Karabas-tov spring in Turkistan region, Kazakhstan – *R.turanus forma karabasicus*;
- from springs near the village of Galkina (Turkistan region) – *R.subaequalis*, *R.turanus karabasicus morpha excisus*, and *R.subaequalis forma zarudnyi*;
- from the Koylik area of the Chirchik Basin – *R.turanus natio kuilkensis*;
- from flowing waters in the Zhambyl region, Kazakhstan – *R.brevicornis*, *R.turanus* subspecies *coxalis*, and *R. hirsutus morpha hirsutissimus*;
- from springs in Shymkent – *R.gracilis*, later renamed by G. Karaman (1984) as *Gammarus chimkenti*;
- from irrigation canals near Talas, Kyrgyzstan – *R.subaequalis* forma *bianchi*.

An analysis of historical and contemporary studies on the amphipod (Malacostraca: Amphipoda) fauna of Uzbekistan's Chirchik Basin and adjacent mountainous areas indicates that this group of aquatic organisms plays a significant role in the region's ecological stability and biological diversity. The research findings, particularly the scientific legacy of A.V.Martynov, have laid the foundation for the taxonomy and morphological characterization of amphipods in the region.

Below is a modern systematic list of amphipod species from the Chirchik Basin and adjacent areas, compiled based on the literature:

Gammaridae Latreille, 1802

Gammarus Fabricius, 1775

1. *Gammarus turanus* (Martynov, 1935)
2. *Gammarus subaequalis* (Martynov, 1935)
3. *Gammarus brevicornis* (Martynov, 1935)
4. *Gammarus hirsutus* (Martynov, 1935)
5. *Gammarus gracilis* (Martynov, 1935) = *Gammarus chimkenti* (Karaman, 1984)

The regional distribution of findings related to this macrozoobenthic group has been recorded in areas such as Chimyonsoy, Karabas-tov, Galkina, Koylik, Shymkent, and other locations, highlighting the ecological adaptability of amphipods. The morphological differentiation among amphipod species is attributed to their adaptation to hydrological and abiotic conditions. However, the fragmented and unsystematized nature of the existing data calls for a comprehensive reevaluation based on ecological and molecular approaches.

The analysis of this study reveals that the amphipod fauna of the Chirchik Basin and its surrounding regions has not yet been fully explored from a scientific perspective. Existing data are primarily based on historical research and lack systematic precision. While A.V.Martynov's work serves as a foundational source in this field, there is a clear need for new investigations employing modern ecological and genetic methods.

References

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